

Earthquakes and tectonic shifts in the regional orders

Tunç Aybak¹

Abstract:

Natural disasters are not only ruptures in the crust of the earth but also have the potential to trigger tectonic geopolitical changes that go beyond the national territories with short- and long-term foreign policy implications. The recent earthquake in Turkey was not the first but one of the worst natural disasters in modern history in terms of its scale and scope. The earthquake hit 10 out of the 81 provinces in Turkey, which contain the home towns of 13.4 million people including the Syrian refugees alongside with the towns and cities on Turkish Syrian border. The earthquake was felt as far as Israel, Palestine, Egypt, Palestine, Lebanon, Cyprus, and the Black Sea coast of Turkey, followed by more than 2,100 aftershocks. The aim of this paper is to assess the geopolitical implications of the recent earthquake in Turkey for the future regional orders in the Middle East, the Caucasus and the Eastern Mediterranean.

Keywords:

Neo-Ottomanism, Earthquake Diplomacy, Foreign Policy, Geopolitics, Refugees

¹ Director of MA International Relations Programme at School of Law, Middlesex University.

Earthquake diplomacy

It was the earthquake in 1999 in Marmara that defused the confrontational diplomatic style between Greece and Turkey. The ongoing ethnic conflict between Turkish and Greek Cypriots in Cyprus in 1975 and the following invasion and conflicting territorial disputes in the Aegean had interrupted the tentative attempts at reconciliation. In 1996 a war was only narrowly escaped. It was the earthquake in Marmara region in August 1999 that created a favourable and empathetic atmosphere in both countries. This was further endorsed in October by Turkish demonstrations of sympathy when Athens, too, was hit by an earthquake. A new “earthquake diplomacy” appeared to be emerging. Some factors played an important role in the earthquake diplomacy between Greece and Turkey. First both parties focused on the low politics issues on which there is no conflict. Secondly, the societal engagement on both sides involved 130 Greek and Turkish NGOs including local government cooperation on both sides of the borders. Third, the media representations have encouraged the public perceptions to move from enmity to more friendly environment. Despite the cooperative atmosphere created as a result Marmara earthquake in 1999, the link between the earthquake diplomacy and foreign policy strategies are still debatable. Ker-Lindsay for instance warns against the simplistic assumptions that diplomatic efforts should be causally linked with the occurrence of disasters. Instead he asserts that disasters may have multiplying and legitimizing effect on diplomatic rapprochement (Ker-Lindsay, 2000).

On the other hand, some scholars who contributed to the disaster diplomacy literature in examining the conditions under which disasters can lead to long-term disaster-related collaboration at both governmental and non-governmental level among states in conflict. Ganabati et al. argue, focusing on the role of the 1999 earthquake, acknowledge the diversity and complexity of disaster diplomacy situations that may lead to long-term disaster-related cooperation among states in conflict when: (1) one party providing disaster relief to another party is followed by a similar reciprocal gesture (i.e. tit-for-tat diplomacy); (2) there is a realization and acceptance that neighbours should come to each other’s assistance in times of disaster; and (3) there is an enabling broader context (e.g. a rapprochement process) conducive to sustaining the long-term cooperation (Ganabati et al. 2010).

The jury is still out whether earthquakes and disasters may lead to rapprochement and more conciliatory diplomatic demarches. In this paper, I will concentrate on the foreign policy implications of the earthquake that hit South East Turkey in February and the following earthquake diplomacy and cooperative efforts between Turkey and . This is not a random selection. These countries are selected on the basis that Turkey has had problematic relations. These neighbouring countries are also directly affected by Turkey’s grand designs and ambitions of its foreign policy strategy.

The rise and fall Neo-Ottomanism:

It is worth putting these developments in the context of Turkish grand foreign policy strategy of Neo-Ottomanism that is the driving force in Turkey's regional hegemonic policy strategy. It was mainly the Prime Minister Davutoglu, formerly in charge of Turkish foreign policy, has been the main strategist behind this Neo-Ottomanist drive. His concept of 'strategic depth' can be located within this new transitional pan-Islamist geopolitical vision (Davutoglu, 2014). Strategic depth is the geopolitical discourse concerning Turkey's position that provides a new direction to increase the power of Turkey in those regions with which claims that Turkey has privileged national interests and close religious and cultural ties that stem from the legacies of the Ottoman Empire as the protectorate of the Sunni Muslims against the Christian west and non-Sunni nations. Davutoglu's key argument is that the civilizational conflict between the Christian West and Islamic Turkey is irreconcilable in the long run. Instead Turkey needs to increase its influence by utilizing its geostrategic location and its Ottoman legacy in its immediate neighbourhoods. This can clearly be still discerned in Turkey's foreign policy actions towards Syria, Armenia and Greece. Since the Syrian crisis unravelled in 2013, Turkey has openly adopted a sectarian policy supporting the Sunni opposition forces against the Assad regime. Despite the declining personal influence of Davutoglu since his resignation, this increasingly confrontational strategy still informs Turkey's foreign policy conduct in relation to Armenia Syria and Greece as manifested in Erdogan's siege mentality discourse that Turkey is surrounded by arch enemies.

In the past, Turkey was favourably treated in the Middle East, the Balkans, and Europe. Surprisingly, the situation had altered so drastically in the early 2010s following the Arab Spring that Kalin, an adviser to the then-prime minister Erdogan and currently the Director of National Intelligence (MIT) described Turkey's situation as one of "precious loneliness," contending that Turkey was marginalised in the international community and surrounded by potential competitors who do not want Turkey to succeed in the region and beyond because it was standing up for its religious values and Ottomanist foreign policy ideals. It is obvious that Turkey's position in the world has changed since then testing the geopolitical ambitions under Erdogan's regime (Atmaca, et al. 2022) Even before the earthquake, it was obvious that Turkey's Neo-Ottomanist drive in the region faced structural obstacles isolating Turkey even further in its immediate region. The confrontation with Greece on the Cyprus Issue and energy exploration in the Eastern Mediterranean region in its militaristic posture towards Armenia on the side of Azerbaijan undermined Turkey's hegemonic intent as an influencer the Balkans, the Middle East and the Southern Caucasus. As Ozel and Balta pertinently argued '... while the fears and ambitions of the political elites paved the way for certain foreign policy choices, at each critical juncture these policy choices Turkey's Foreign Policy were either constrained or enabled by more systemic factors. The result was a foreign policy posture that is perceived to be incoherent and irrational, since it combined both Turkey's grandiose fantasies about being a major power with its

long-held fears and insecurities' (Balta and Ozel, 2021, 557) In this context, it can be argued that to a certain extent, the earthquake in February 2023 played a role of catalyst in the gradual transformation Turkey's foreign policy strategy and its diplomatic style from more belligerent to more accommodating diplomatic style. It must be noted however that any conclusive analysis could be too premature at this point even though some early indicators may shed light on its changing bilateral relations with Armenia, Greece and Syria. Let us look at these bilateral cases in turn in the light of post-earthquake developments in Turkey's immediate neighbourhood.

Syria: from confrontation to rapprochement?

Turkey's bilateral relations with Syria during the Cold War as a NATO member was determined by the Cold War divisions between the Soviet Union and the west. Some territorial issues remained, particularly in Hatay's status- a historically disputed region. The presence of the Kurdish separatists (PKK) in Syria remained another source constant friction. With the end of the Cold War, however, Turkey's immediate neighbourhood was opened for economic penetration. Turkey's economic drive to the Middle East began in the 1990s under various coalition governments. The strong growth of the Middle Eastern economies since the start of the oil boom in 2003 and the rise of the Anatolian business interests penetrating the Middle East in general and trade with Syria along the border. Turkey's so-called success story was more or less facilitated by external circumstances, it is by no means to suggest that the hegemonic model the AKP did not play a key role. As policy brief published in 2008 by SETA foundation for Political, Economic and Social Research-pro-government think tank- summarised 'The rise to power of Turkish Prime Minister Tayyip Erdoğan marks a new era in positive Turkish-Syrian relations. The new Syrian attitude towards Turkey represents a break from past: Syria considers Turkey a reliable partner for brokering a peace deal between Syria and Israel, and Turkey offers opportunities for political and economic cooperation for improving the welfare and security of two countries.' (Moubayet, 2008, 3)

After a decade of cooperation with Syria, Turkey's policy has changed radically as a result of the 2011–12 civil uprisings providing a geopolitical opportunity for Erdoğan's Neo-Ottomanist strategy towards Syria. Erdoğan openly started to call for the overthrow of President Bashar al-Assad's regime and actively sponsored the Sunni opposition and radical insurgency groups. Since March 2011 Turkey has escalated its hostile policy towards Assad regime by cutting diplomatic ties; and, supporting and aiding Syria's political and armed opposition. Turkey's direct military intervention against the Assad regime involved imposition of a no-fly zone or humanitarian corridors for Syrian refugees and military incursions into the Syrian territory to punish Kurds and undermine the self-declared autonomous Rojava canton within Syrian territories. (Cagatay, 2020) However, The recent regional developments exposed the limitations of Erdoğan's agency and his aim to overthrow the regime as Turkey's Neo-Ottomanist strategy that has been confronted by the

systemic and structural constraints at the regional and global level, clashing with Russia's overall strategic objectives in the Middle East as well as the strategic differences between the US and Turkey in relation to the Kurds in Syria (Ozel and Ozkan, 2015). One of the unintended consequences of Turkey's foreign policy in relation to Syria has been the exponential influx of Syrian refugees into Turkey. Currently the number of Syrian refugees settled in Turkey reached roughly 3.6 million which is the biggest issue for the government blurring the boundaries between domestic and foreign policy. Turkey's Syrian foreign policy has been increasingly unsustainable. Since late 2021 to early 2022, Ankara has been promoting two seemingly irreconcilable goals. On the one hand, it has threatened to launch an invasion of northern Syria with military force. Nevertheless, despite continuing drone attacks against prominent Kurdish officials by Turkey with the objective of consolidating victories made in the northeast, Ankara did not launch a land offensive due to a lack of support from Russia, Iran, and the United States. The Erdogan administration has also been working to patch fences with Bashar al-Assad at the same time. The efforts of Ankara to normalise relations with Assad complement those being made in the region to forge alliances. The readmission of Assad to the Arab League, as well as rapprochement between Saudi Arabia and Iran, Arab states and Israel, and Arab Gulf monarchies are all positive regional developments.

However, despite Turkish drone operations against the Kurdish strongholds in Syria. A crucial conference between the defence ministers of Russia, Turkey, and Syria, along with their respective security chiefs, took place in Moscow in December 2022, sparking the process of rapprochement just before the February 2023 Earthquake. (The Guardian, 2022) Normalization between Turkey and Syria was also evident before the recent elections after the earthquake. Moscow hosted a meeting between the defence ministers of Russia, Iran, Syria and Turkey on April 25, as well as the first official meeting of foreign ministers on May 10. There, according to former Turkish foreign minister Mevlüt Çavuşoğlu, the ministers discussed the importance of collaborating to combat terrorism, facilitate the safe return of refugees, and safeguard Syria's territorial integrity.

The earthquake severely damaged the already precarious Syrian refugees in South East Turkey, exposing Erdogan's shortcomings in his approach to refugees. Despite this, the tragedy did not lead to any change in Turkey's stance toward Syria, whose northern regions, including Turkish-controlled Afrin, also experienced widespread death and destruction as a result of the earthquakes. In order to facilitate the flow of UN-coordinated humanitarian aid, Ankara agreed to reopen two border crossings for three months in addition to the one on the border with Idlib. However, it has refused to permit Syrians to enter Turkey. While the Syrian government-controlled border crossings and those leading to Kurdish-held regions are still closed, all three border crossings are open to areas controlled by the rebels. Turkey-backed forces blocked aid convoys from the Kurdish-run northeast for days. (Arab Centre, 2023)

This attitude implies that the feeling of shared suffering has not led to any moderation on the part of Turkey toward Syria and that rigid conditions still apply

to Russian-mediated efforts to mend ties between Ankara and Damascus. Many Syrian refugees still live in misery and uncertainty in the provinces of Turkey that were devastated by the earthquake. Syrians are facing growing public pressure to return home as Ankara struggles to meet the needs of the affected population. The Turkish government and local authorities are increasingly using xenophobic and derogatory tactics against Syrian refugees living there. 2020.3 Financial Times Hatred and anti-refugee sentiments are already at an all-time high, and many Turks now see the disaster as a chance to send the refugees home. (Hurseda Haber, 2023)

Since late 2021 Erdogan on several occasions has threatened to launch an invasion of northern Syria with military force. The development of an autonomous Kurdish political entity under the administration of the PYD/YPG continues to be the main source of tension between Syria and Turkey, according to President Erdogan (Foreign Policy, 2023) However, Ankara's top objective right now is to repatriate Syrian refugees and reach an agreement with the Syrian regime. President Erdogan also made clear that Turkish construction companies could benefit from the resettlement of the Syrian refugees in Syria. Before the earthquake, Erdogan and Assad had reached an understanding regarding the removal of the US-supported Kurdish presence from northern Syria. As a response, Assad made normalising ties with Ankara contingent on Turkey withdrawing its troops from northwest Syria, allowing the Syrian government to retake the area. Erdogan, however, would be more eager than ever to negotiate an arrangement with Assad to ensure the return of 3.6 million Syrian refugees to Syria given the public anger directed at the presence of Syrian refugees in Turkey during the election campaign after the earthquake. Despite the earthquake, the obstacles to reconciliation between Turkey and Syria persist particularly in the areas of border issues and Turkey's interventionist posture in the Syrian territories. In fact, as it was rightly observed by an analyst, Syria's reconciliation with the Arab League may end the Syrian isolation and diminish the possibility of diplomatic rapprochement between Turkey and Syria. (Arab Centre, March 29 2023).

Greece: Rekindling Earthquake Diplomacy

The earthquake also offered an opportunity to rekindle the earthquake diplomacy between Turkey and Greece. Greece was one of the first countries that sent aid to Turkey, despite the fact that before the earthquake Turkey and Greece were on the brink of a military confrontation over territorial disputes in the Aegean Sea and the exploration of the gas deposits over the disputed territorial water. (Greek Reporter) Erdoğan on several occasions adopted a threatening posture against Greece that Turkey might “come all of a sudden during the night” and that Turkish missiles could strike Athens if Greece did not “keep quiet.” (Financial Times, September 2022) This was followed by Greece's post-earthquake goodwill gesture, Erdoğan took a call from Greek Prime Minister Kyriakos Mitsotakis, thus backing down from a prior statement that he would never speak to him again. And Turkish Foreign Minister Mevlut Cavusoglu hosted his Greek counterpart Nikos Dendias,

who visited earthquake-affected areas in Hatay near the Syrian border and stressed the need to improve relations. (AL Jazeera, February 2023) The Greek citizens and NGOs were also actively involved in the delivery of aid and rescue operations. (Aljazeera, February 2023) During Dendias' visit, the Turkish Foreign Minister said that in 1999, as an ordinary citizen, he had written a letter to TIMES magazine he had argued that Greece and Turkey should not wait until the next earthquake to improve their relations. (Reuters, 2023)

Despite the diplomatic demarches, the key issues between Greece and Turkey remain unresolved as geopolitical claims still stand in the way of real and deep cooperation. For instance, Turkey still pursues a long-term objective of exercising its influence and exploration of gas in the Eastern Mediterranean as this was manifested by its Blue Homeland (Mavi Vatan) strategy. (Candar, 2020) While Greece forged an alliance with Cyprus, Egypt and Israel in 2019 with an Eastern Mediterranean Gas forum, which envisages the exploitation and marketing of the gas deposits. Turkey refuses to recognize the maritime borders of Greece and Cyprus and was left out of this alliance. The issues in the delineation of maritime borders and armament of the Aegean Islands still have the potential to restart frictions. This risk is even further enhanced as the Lausanne Treaty, signed at the end of the Turkish-Greek war in 1923, which laid the foundations and settled the borders between two countries nearly 100 years ago, is coming under Erdogan's scrutiny as a result of the change of public perceptions in Turkey. (The Conversation, February 2023).

Armenia: from confrontation to normalization

Turkey and Armenia have had a difficult relationship over the past few decades. Turkey was one of the first countries to recognize Armenian independence after the end of the Soviet Union in 1991, but relations between the states quickly deteriorated after Armenia's invasion of Nagorno Karabakh, a disputed region in Azerbaijan in the early 1990s. By 1993, diplomatic relations between Turkey and Armenia had ended and Turkey's border with Armenia was closed. Since then Turkey has actively supported oil-rich Azerbaijan as a decades-old territorial dispute flared anew into an armed conflict over Nagorno-Karabakh, a mountainous region situated within Azerbaijan controlled by Armenia-backed ethnic separatists. Despite an attempt at reconciliation in 2009, Turkish President Recep Tayyip Erdogan had to step back from diplomatic rapprochement with Armenia due to the Azeri objections. As a result, Erdogan made the establishment of formal ties with Armenia conditional on its withdrawal from Nagorno-Karabakh. (Aydintasbas et al, 2023) In the military clashes between Armenia and Azerbaijan over Nagorno Karabakh in 2020, Turkish President Recep Tayyip Erdogan openly declared his government's support for Azerbaijan extending its military aid and supplying drones to the Azerbaijani military. (New Yorker, 2022)

However, despite these long-standing differences, disaster diplomacy can build on actions taken in the months since the earthquake in Turkey and Armenia. For instance, the foreign ministers of Turkey and Armenia met to talk about the likelihood of diplomatic normalization. As part of talks to normalize relations, both parties have designated special envoys to mediate; Turkish and Armenian airlines have resumed operating direct flights between the two nations; and Armenia lifted its import ban on Turkey last year. Additionally, there is a chance for Ankara and Yerevan to normalize relations because of the ongoing peace negotiations between Armenia and Azerbaijan. Turkey and Armenia may be able to maintain the open border for trade and commerce in the near future by building on the momentum created by the earthquake.

In fact, the Armenian government was one of the first countries to send food, medicine, drinking water and other emergency supplies to devastated cities and towns soon after the quakes. Armenian research and rescue crews also actively engaged in search and rescue operation on the ground. Armenian crews taking part in rescue operations in the region Gaziantep and Kahramanmaras, where large Armenian communities lived in the past, was highly symbolic. More importantly, the aid from Armenia crossed into Turkey through the land border which has been closed by the Turkish authorities since the early 1990s was the most significant gesture. Armenian Prime Minister Pashinyan called Turkish President Recep Tayyip Erdogan to express his condolences, while Armenian Foreign Minister Mirzoyan visited Turkey on February 15 to meet with his counterpart, both parties expressed their willingness to strengthen diplomatic relations. While Mirzoyan requested the full opening of the border between Turkey and Armenia, Cavusoglu's emphasis was that progress in the normalization of relations between Armenia and Turkey, should contribute to peace and prosperity in the region, he proposed that finding a peaceful solution to the issues between Yerevan and Baku was a central condition before opening the Turkish border with Armenia. (Daily Sabah, 12 March 2023] Despite the earthquake diplomacy, Turkey exercises caution not to alienate its traditional ally Azerbaijan.

Conclusion

The question remains: Can disasters induce cooperation amongst hostile countries? Earthquakes undoubtedly have geopolitical implications for societies and states. Disasters can have positive transformative potential as people are brought together in common humanity. This also applies to inter-state relations and nations. Earthquakes and disasters may transform the changing relations between citizens and their states in the wake of tectonic shifts. On the other hand, disaster diplomacy on its own does not resolve interstate conflict but opens up for the channels of communication and societal interaction that may influence public perceptions. As the evidence demonstrates that disaster-related activities can act as catalysis diplomatic activities if actors choose, disaster diplomacy can be put into practice.

As the events unfolded, the earthquake definitely undermined Erdogan's polarizing foreign discourse that Turkey is surrounded by enemies driven by 'we versus them' mindset. The earthquake is not just a sudden rupture a tectonic shift in the crust of the earth but also shake individual and national identities and certainties offering uncertainty but also diplomatic opportunity. The Lisbon earthquake of 1755 caused Voltaire, Rousseau and others to herald the death of God and the beginning of humanism and enlightenment. Just after the earthquake Erdogan declared that the earthquake was 'god's will'. The following election victory reaffirmed Erdogan's religious take on the earthquakes supported by populist national and religious majority.

The earthquakes also trigger diplomatic processes and open up new channels of communication. In the case of Syria, the earthquake did not really lead to diplomatic thaw but created further frictions over border issues and collaboration. In the case of Armenia, the new communication channels have been opened and triggered some good diplomacy starting the conversation between parties which has been absent for a long time. With Greece the relations have been rekindled and the hostile language has been abandoned.

In general disaster have the potential to play the role of a catalyst. However, they cannot alter the grand strategies and long-term objectives in the exercise of foreign policy.

References:

- Al Jazeera, Accessed, 27 February 2023 <https://www.al-monitor.com/originals/2023/02/quake-disaster-delivers-diplomatic-silver-lining-turkey>
- Arab Center. Accessed 23 June 2023 <https://arabcenterdc.org/resource/disaster-politics-and-earthquake-diplomacy-in-syria-and-turkey/>
- Arab Centre, Accessed 29 June 2023 <https://arabcenterdc.org/resource/obstacles-to-a-turkey-syria-reconciliation/>
- Aydintasbas, Asli. and Giragosian, Richard. 2023 Acts of normality: The potential for Turkey-Armenia rapprochement, *European Council of Foreign Affairs*, Accessed 15 March 2023 <https://ecfr.eu/publication/acts-of-normality-the-potential-for-turkey-armenia-rapprochement/>
- Atmaca, Ayşe Ömür and Torun, Zerrin. 2022 “Geopolitical Visions in Turkish Foreign Policy”. *Journal of Balkan and Near Eastern Studies*. Vol. 24, no 1, 114–137
- Aydintasbas. Asli et al. 2023 [<https://ecfr.eu/publication/acts-of-normality-the-potential-for-turkey-armenia-rapprochement/>]
- Balta, Evren and Özel, Soli. 2021 "Turkey's Foreign Policy: Opportunities and Constraints in a New Era." *Social Research: An International Quarterly*, Vol. 88 no. 2, 539-560
- Cagatay, Soner, 2022 ‘Erdoğan’s “Mini Empire” in Libya and Syria’ Turkey Scope Vol. 4, No. 3 . Accessed 17 July, <https://www.washingtoninstitute.org/media/726>
- Candar, Cengiz, *The Turkey Analyst*, August 2020 Accessed, 17 June 2023 <https://www.turkeyanalyst.org/publications/turkey-analyst-articles/item/648-turkey%E2%80%99s-blue-homeland-doctrine-signaling-perpetual-conflict-in-the-mediterranean-and-rough-waters-ahead.html>
- The Conversation, Accessed February 2023 <https://theconversation.com/why-do-so-many-turkish-people-believe-secret-clauses-in-the-1923-lausanne-treaty-will-be-unveiled-this-year-197296>
- Daily Sabah, February 15 2023, Accessed 19 February 2023 <https://www.dailysabah.com/politics/diplomacy/turkiye-hails-armenias-friendly-gesture-after-earthquake>).
- Daily Sabah, 12 March 2023, Accessed 12 May 2023 <https://www.dailysabah.com/politics/diplomacy/turkish-armenian-ministers-hold-fruitful-constructive-meeting>
- Financial Times, Accessed 14 February 2023, <https://www.ft.com/content/fffc2928-df29-43ed-ab88-bef0fa9df81d>

Financial Times, [Turkey's tough talk on Greece fuels Aegean tensions | Financial Times \(ft.com\)](#)

Greek Reporter, Accessed 8 March 2023, <https://greekreporter.com/2023/02/06/turkey-earthquake-greece-sends-help/>

The Guardian, Accessed 29 December 2022 <https://www.theguardian.com/world/2022/dec/29/turkish-and-syrian-defence-and-security-officials-meet-for-first-time-in-decade>

Foreign Policy, [Accessed 14 May 2023 <https://foreignpolicy.com/2023/03/26/turkey-stateless-syrians-earthquake-elections-erdogan-assad/>

Davutoglu, Ahmet. 2014. *Stratejik Derinlik*, Kure Yayinlari

Ganapati, N. E., Kelman, I., & Koukis, T. 2010. "Analysing Greek-Turkish disaster-related cooperation: A disaster diplomacy perspective". *Cooperation and Conflict*, 45(2), 162–185.

Hurseda Haber, Accessed 14 May 2023 <https://hurseda.net/fehim-tastekin/50953/deprem-turkiye-nin-dusmanlik-hatlarini-kismen-catirdatti.html>

Ker-Lindsay, James. 2000. "Greek-Turkish rapprochement: The impact of disaster diplomacy" *Cambridge Review of International Affairs*, 14:1, 215-232.

Moubayet, Sami. "Turkish-Syrian Relations: Erdogan's Legacy", *Seta Policy Brief* October 2008, No25. Accessed 12/07/2023, http://setadc.org/wp-content/uploads/2015/05/SETA_Policy_Brief_No_25_Sami_Moubayed.pdf.

New Yorker, Accessed 22 May 2022, <https://www.newyorker.com/magazine/2022/05/16/the-turkish-drone-that-changed-the-nature-of-warfare>

Ozel, Soli and Ozkan, Behlul, 2015 "Illusions versus reality: Turkey's approach to the Middle East and North Africa", Policy Brief, *FRIDE*, no 200. Accessed July 2023, https://www.files.ethz.ch/isn/190156/Illusions%20versus%20reality_%20Turkey%E2%80%99s%20approach%20to%20the%20Middle%20East%20and%20North%20Afric.pdf

Reuters, Accessed 20 June 2023 <https://www.reuters.com/world/leaders-turkey-greece-vow-repair-ties-after-year-tension-2023-07-12/>

Ter-Matevosyan, Varham, 2021. Deadlocked in history and geopolitics: Revisiting Armenia–Turkey relations, *Digest of Middle East Studies* (DEMO) Volume 30, Issue 3